

CUSTOMERS PARTICIPATION AND CONSUMERS ETHICAL PERCEPTION OF SHARING ECONOMY ON WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM PRICE: ROLE OF VALUE CO-CREATION INTENTIONS AND SOCIAL VALUE CREATION

NUSWANTORO SETYADI PRADONO^{*1}, HENDAR², ANY SETYARINI³ and EDY SURYAWARDANA⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Management Department, Sultan Agung Islamic University, Semarang City, Indonesia.

*Correspondence Email: nuswantoropradono@gmail.com

Abstract

Purpose –The purpose of this paper is to investigate and examine the roles of value co-creation intentions (VCI) and social value creation (SVC) in mediating the relationship between customer participation (CP) and consumer ethical perception of the sharing economy (CEP) with the willingness to pay premium price (WPP). **Design/methodology/approach** - This paper selected 402 consumers who used the sharing economy platform in Indonesia and examined the regression relationship of the five constructs using SEM with AMOS 22.0. **Findings** –The findings showed that CP and CEP showed important antecedents for SVC and VCI and both have positive effects on WPP. This indicated that VCI and SVC have important roles as mediators in the relationship between CP and CEP with WPP. **Originality/value** - By examining literature related to customer behaviour, customer ethics, value co-creation, and sharing economy platform, this paper offers a unique analysis of the relation roadmap for customer participation and customer ethics with the willingness to pay premium price.

Keywords: Value Co-Creation Intentions, Social Value Creation, Customer Participation, Consumer Ethical Perception, Willingness to Pay Premium Price.

Paper Type – Research Paper

INTRODUCTION

Along with the development of information technology, sharing economy in marketing practice is a new popular culture made by transactions through online platforms as the main authorized capital (Bucher, E., Fieseler, C., Lutz, 2016). Belk (2014) explained sharing economy as the acquisition or distribution of resources coordinated or executed by many people to get certain compensation or costs. This sharing scheme provides various alternative options that are affordable and can be done comfortably by stable companies (Eckhardt, G.M., Bardhi, 2016), enabling people to use underutilized assets through cost-based sharing (Zervas, G., Proserpio, D., Byers, 2017), and leasing their property for the needs of others for a limited time (Mittendorf, 2016; Teubner, T., & Flath, 2019).

Sharing economy is considered as a culture that engages many people by utilizing their assets with others through online sharing economy platforms (SEP) (Bucher, E., Fieseler, C., Lutz, 2016). SEP becomes a means of gathering people in an active role to create value through relationships and experiences, so it becomes a fundamental system in marketing practice

(Perren, R., & Kozinets, 2018). Through SEP, service providers and consumers interact to make business transaction deals. SEP has become a mediation platform that plays an important role in changing behaviour to make transactions (Perren, R., & Kozinets, 2018).

SEP is a new research area and at the individual level, there are still many people who have not focused on supporting the mastery of related knowledge (Zach, W. Y. L., Chan, T. K. H., Balaji, M. S., & Chong, 2018). Themes of research that have been conducted in the SEP field among others why people participate in collaborative consumption needs and why people are attracted to use SEP over and over again (Hamari, J., Sjöklint, M., Ukkonen, 2016; Möhlmann, 2015). Studies conducted on ethics reveal that privacy and security risks are inhibiting factors in the use of SEP. However, the results of other studies emphasize the need of in-depth exploration on ethical aspects (Zach, W. Y. L., Chan, T. K. H., Balaji, M. S., & Chong, 2018; Perren, R., & Kozinets, 2018; Sutherland, W., & Jarrahi (2018).

SEP operates as a mediator and gives consumers the freedom to contribute to the solutions that are appropriate to the specific context and goals of each consumer. According to WeEconomy (2015), SEP enables consumers to find their own solutions, and this which later will increase consumer participation in the form of support from other members and their communities. SEP empowers consumers to participate in a way that allows them to negotiate in determining their own solutions. This is an important aspect of value co-creation, either in the form of value co-creation intention or another form such as social value co-creation.

In maintaining competitiveness, value co-creation has recently emerged as a business major strength (Merz, M.A., Zarantonello, L., Grappi, 2018; Zwass, 2010). Research conducted by Prahalad, C.K., Ramaswamy (2004) stated that sharing economy platforms are media for value co-creation. By prioritizing services, it will create value creation that results from a joint production process by providers and consumers. Through interaction and communication, consumers see various value co-creations that can increase the value of willingness to pay (WTP) for the premium price of service convenience.

Park (2018) explained the need for further studies that focus on actual consumer purchasing behaviour such as whether the same consumer purchases certain types of consumption ethically. The research results are expected to improve the type of ethical consumption in addition to paying attention to the discussion of ethical consumption analysis comprehensively. Meanwhile, a study conducted by Shao & Ünal (2019) only focuses on the effect of attributes related to sustainability and availability for willingness to pay premium prices. However, there is a tendency for consumers to do activities that are not related to the sustainability of attributes such as performance, aesthetics, brand reputation, quality, and others. In consequence, to determine the willingness of consumers to make purchases at premium prices on products with consumer ethical perceptions is an area of further research. This study attempts to explain the road map in which CP and CEP affect WPP.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sharing Economy Platform (SEP)

Sharing economy is the process of distributing assets to others to be used and operationalized and then receiving and taking things from other people to use (Belk, 2014). According to Eckhardt, G., Bardhi (2015), sharing economy is more than just sharing, it also concerns commercial aspects and its broad implications. Sharing economy as capitalism based on the crowd (Sundararajan, 2016), the phenomena of consumption collaborations (Botsman, R., Rogers, (2011), a form of acquisition or distribution of resources coordinated by people for costs or compensation which can be done in the form of trade, exchange, and barter (Belk (2014). In addition, sharing economy is considered as monetization of the form of short-term leases of underutilized assets by service providers which can be individuals or companies. Thus, sharing economy is the capitalization of underutilized resources based on compensation or fees by service providers, both individuals and companies (Kumar, V., Lahiri, A., Dogan, 2018).

SEP is a sharing economy system that places the consumers at the starting point of all consumer-to-consumer interactions. In this system, the consumers independently contribute to solutions according to the specific problems of each consumer. Thus, it will increase consumer participation in the form of support from the community (We-Economy, 2015). Consumer participation will be an important aspect of the emergence of value co-creation.

Willingness to Pay Premium Price

The concept of willingness to pay premium (WPP) refers to the maximum amount of money that consumers are willing to spend on particular products or services (Homburg, C., Koschate, N., Hoyer, 2005). This concept applies to all product prices that do not characterize market rules. In determining prices, product marketing and development management, as well as the willingness of customers have important roles (Breidert, C., Hahsler, M. and Reutterer, 2006; Fleischman Foreit, K.G. and Foreit, 2004; Tu et al., 2018). Based on this matter, the small variance will have a strong impact on consumer behaviour, income, and profits (Marn, M.V., Roegner, E.V. and Zawada, 2003). WPP is often regarded as one of the strongest results of loyalty and a key measure of brand equity (Li, G., Li, G., Kambele, 2012; Palmatier, R.W., Scheer, L.K., Steenkamp, 2007).

Research conducted by Breidert, C., Hahsler, M., and Reutterer, (2006) argued that the concept of WPP is a domain of consumer behaviour in marketing that accurately predicts purchasing behaviour which helps organizations to develop pricing strategies (De Pelsmacker, P., Driesen, L., Rayp, 2005).

Premium price is defined as an excess payment paid above the average as a result of an improvement in the quality of a product or service (Rao, A.R. , Bergen, 1992). According to (Pandey, N., Mehta, N., Roy, 2016 and Marn, M. V., Roegner, E. V., & Zawada, 2004), WPP will significantly affect revenue and profit. WPP is consumers' willingness to pay more for a certain brand of service compared to other similar brands (Netemeyer et al., 2004). WPP is a

strategic program of each business organization as customers' willingness to pay premium prices which can result in higher profitability and sustainable competitive advantage for the organization. WPP is a function of one's perception of brand value and quality since higher prices reflect the higher value and better quality (Davicik, N. & Sharma, 2015). WPP is also often considered as one of the dominant factors of loyalty and a key measure of brand equity (Li, G., Li, G., Kambele, 2012; Palmatier, R.W., Scheer, L.K., Steenkamp, 2007). WPP is the result of effective brand management related to the ability to set higher prices for all types of brands than competitors' prices (DeChernatony, L., Segal-Horn, 2003a)

Value Co-Creation Intentions

In an effort to maintain competitive advantage, value creation has recently emerged as a major business strength (Merz, M.A., Zarantonello, L., Grappi, 2018; Zwass, 2010). Value co-creation defined as a holistic or iterative management strategy that consolidates different parties to produce valuable products (Prahalad, C.K., Ramaswamy, 2004). Value co-creation is used by companies not only to gain competitive advantages but also for corporate reputation and brand value (Cova, B., Dalli, 2009).

Vargo, S.L., Maglio, P.P., Akaka (2008) described co-creation as the process in such a way which is relying on the efforts of companies, consumers, and other agents thus interdependence and reciprocity are essential for defining interdependent roles, which are consequently related to value creation production and services. It is important to ensure efficient service delivery, customized goods, and more personalized services, consumers must learn to use, maintain, improve, and adapt the offer to their own usage situations, unique needs, and behaviours (Vargo, S.L., Lusch, 2004,2008). Grönroos (2012), exemplified value co-creation in services as a platform for value co-creation occurs on direct interactions between customers and service providers. Apart from different perspectives on value co-creation, all are categorized as having the same concept, that is, direct interaction between providers and customers.

At the operational level, proactive consumers in SEP can mainly participate in the design, testing, conceptualization of services, marketing specialization products/services, and support (Nambisan, S., & Nambisan, 2008; OHern, M. S., & Rindfleisch, 2010). In an effort to encourage consumer participation to increase value co-creation, companies can introduce and offer goods that are more suitable for services to consumers (Bendapudi, N., & Leone, 2003; Firat, A. F., & Venkatesh & Firat, A. F., & Venkatesh, 1993). Therefore, consumer participation has an important role since it is the foundation for the SEP to continue to exist. The consequence that needs to be considered is to measure the value co-creation intention on the sharing economy platform in general, and this is particularly related to consumer ethical perceptions (Nadeem et al., 2019). Based on the description above, the hypothesis that can be proposed is:

H₁: There is a positive relationship between value co-creation intentions and willingness to pay premium.

Customers Participation of SEPs

There are three types of participation (Kamboj, S., & Rahman, 2017) used for participation indicators namely informational participation, actionable participation, and attitudinal participation. Informational participation is the level to obtain information and fulfill the public interest that consumers have in a product or service. According to Nadeem et al., (2019), forms of information participation are frequently providing useful online information to other members, frequently posting messages, and giving responses online at SEP. Actionable participation is defined as the extent to which consumers often participate and interact with each other in SEP activities. Forms of participation that can be followed up include participating actively and spending lots of time online in SEP activities. Attitudinal participation is a psychological tendency to evaluate SEP's performance by like or dislike assessment criteria and have positive or negative attitudes towards products or services from the platform in general (Kamboj, S., & Rahman, 2017). Forms of attitudinal participation include participating in this SEP will be good and beneficial for consumers. Botsman, R. and Rogers (2011) argued that sharing economy is an expansion of the concept of collaborative consumption by adopting information and communication technology (ICT) and the development of a collaborative web community to reduce transaction costs. Sharing economy, also referred to as peer-to-peer platforms, has provided the possibility for people to use their underutilized inventory through cost-based sharing, thus potentially reducing individual waste by maximizing the utilization of existing consumption (Belk, 2014; Zervas, G., Proserpio, D., Byers, 2017). In sharing economy, customer is one of the important elements especially in the participation for profit. Customer involvement is a form of customer participation and engagement. Customer involvement with the intensity of individual participation can be defined as customer involvement in the service production, or provision, or even distribution of information (Auh, S., Bell, S.J., McLeod, C.S., Shih, 2007; Chan, K.W., Yim, C.K., Lam, 2010). On the other hand, it is possible for consumers to have the ability to use options that affect the order and substance of the service delivery process. Customers provide feedback to the company to get closer and generate loyalty, and customers who participate in product development tend to be repeat customers who are willing to buy more of the company's products (Merlo, O., Eisingerich, A.B., Auh, 2014). SEP exists because of the consumers' active online participation. On the other hand, SEP will not exist if no one participates in it. Consumer participation of SEP and its successful development can be a major challenge. Consumer participation in SEP refers to efforts to achieve value co-creation through mandatory but voluntary participation in service production and delivery processes (Chae, H., & Ko 2016; Kamboj, S., & Sarmah, 2018). Previous studies stated that participation is also defined as interaction, which is the role of online members participating actively in online platform activities. Consumer participation in the existence of an online platform will provide additional assurance that the online platform will be successful in running SEP (Koh, J., & Kim, 2004). Thus, the hypothesis that can be proposed is:

H₂: There is a positive relationship between customer participation in SEP and value co-creation intentions.

Consumers Ethical Perception of SEPs

Marketing ethics in general is a systematic study of how moral standards are applied to behaviour, decisions, and institutions (Laczniak, G. R., & Murphy, 2019). Ethics is based on a philosophy of human behaviour related to morality. The word Ethics comes from the Greek word *ethos* which means special. Reference to the academic discipline which studies and analyzes customs, attitudes, values, and rules used in life (Talwar & Ali, 2016). Marketing ethics is broadly defined as a systematic study of how moral standards are applied to behaviour, decisions, and institutions (Laczniak, G. R., & Murphy, 2019).

In the decade of the 1980s, marketing practitioners became more interested in marketing ethics, as indicated by professional organizations and companies starting to adopt codes of ethics in their operations (Agag, 2019). Consequently, since then marketing ethics has become criteria that can be used as references in marketing activities (Ferrell, O. C., Ferrell, L., & Sawayda, 2015; Gaski, 1999; Schauster, E., & Neill, 2017). This study focuses on ethical issues related to transactions in the sharing economy platform (SEP).

SEP acts as a mediator or system vehicle that encourages interaction and facilitates transactions between consumers and service providers by helping them find each other in situations where it will be easier to find (Nadeem et al., 2019). Nadeem et al., (2019) stated that consumer ethical perception is considered as a multidimensional construct consisting of six sub-dimensions, among others privacy, security, fulfillment/reliability, shared value, service recovery, and non-deception. They found a positive relationship between consumer participation and consumer ethical perception, consumer ethical perception and value co-creation intention, as well as consumer participation and value co-creation intention. Participation indicators that include informational, actionable, and attitudinal influence consumer's ethical perception.

Consumer participation can lead to the determination of actual ethical issues related to sharing economy platforms (such as platform security or privacy) that are often exaggerated by service providers (Miyazaki, A. D., & Fernandez, 2001). In SEP, there are a huge data flow and consumer personal information data are exposed to service providers. This will have consequences for ethical problems. More participation can also make consumers clearer about further data collection by SEP. Pai, P. Y., & Tsai, (2011) argued that consumers who participate more in the online platform will get more information which will increase trust in making transactions. Therefore, the increase in consumer participation can increase positive matters regarding ethical perceptions in SEP. Thus the hypothesis that can be proposed is:

H₃: There is a positive relationship between customers participation and consumers ethical perception of SEPs

Koh, J., & Kim, (2004), stated that the number of people participating in SEP will determine the sustainability of the online platforms. Algesheimer, R., Dholakia, U. M., & Herrmann, (2005) said that online platforms strive to encourage consumers to be actively involved thereby creating sustainable relationships. The positive ethical perceptions of consumers about online platforms will affect the intensity of the consumer involvement level (Román, S., & Cuestas, 2008). According to Prahalad, C.K., Ramaswamy,(2004), co-creation is the process of involving

consumers in developing value, in this case, consumers will not be involved if they have feelings of worry. Ind, N., Iglesias, O., dan Schultz, (2013), conveyed that value co-creation reflects participation in culture, that is, consumers looking for opportunities to contribute to social or virtual media, companies can get consumer perceptions on their products or services from this activity. Consumer participation in online platforms can be either positive or negative for the companies. This can affect corporate reputation and image and it is possible that it can affect corporate reputation and image (Veloutsou, C., & Moutinho, 2009). Therefore, value co-creation intention can be greatly influenced by consumer ethical perceptions towards the sellers. Thus, the hypothesis that can be proposed is:

H4: There is a positive relationship between customer ethical perception of SEPs and value co-creation intentions.

Social Value Co-Creation

Customer value is a value in the form of a dynamic concept that may be felt by the customers after the consumption stage (Sánchez, J., Callarisa, L., Rodríguez, R.M., Moliner, 2006), this is related to subjectivity or emotions as customer feedback (Sweeney, J.C., Soutar, 2001). Sánchez, J., Callarisa, L., Rodríguez, R.M., Moliner (2006), argued that learning the perceived value as a whole concept can be categorized into functional value, emotional value, and social value.

Social value comes from the ability of products or services to reinforce or enhance customers' social self-concept (Sweeney, J.C., Soutar, 2001; Wang et al., 2004). Meanwhile, value co-creation is an action that is not realized some while that the activity is done together and each one contributes to the welfare of others (Vargo, S. L., & Lusch, 2016). Social value co-creation can be used to integrate the interests of various entities including profit and non-profit organizations in society. Social value co-creation provides a way to focus on how social goals can be adopted in business activities (Di Domenico et al., 2010), thus providing a bridge between traditional commercial entrepreneurial activity and a more socially oriented view to generate profit. Kroeger & Weber, (2014) argued that for social value co-creation in society, it is needed to emphasize social goals that are in line with the expectations of current society. SEPs stand out when seeking input and interactive discussions can produce useful solutions/answers. This condition encourages consumers to participate more actively (Huang, R., Kim, H., & Kim, 2013) and opens up opportunities for SEP to develop and have continued positive interactions thus creating more value for SEP. For example, in the practice of value co-creation in which the consumer is willing to pay for a convenient and economic transportation option, such as taxi. On the service provider's side, (the driver) delivers the customer and charges the service fee. Thus, if the consumer interest is getting increasing, then the consequence is more service providers will be interested in joining the SEPs platform or conversely. Thus, the hypothesis can be proposed is:

H5: There is a positive relationship between customer participation in SEP and social value co-creation.

Although the existence of SEP is very important, it needs to be given a little consideration to measure consumer intentions in the value co-creation on the platforms used in general and in particular related to consumer ethical perceptions (Nadeem et al., 2019). SEP becomes popular since consumers consider the participation is more convenient, economical, and enjoyable (Zach, W. Y. L., Chan, T. K. H., Balaji, M. S., & Chong, 2018). On the contrary, consumers also have risks associated with the platform and this is related to privacy, security, compliance/reliability, and non-fraud. Dillahunt and Malone, (2015) argued that SEP operates on the principle of sharing information and data input from members. This can result in the risk of information being used for advertisements which is an unwanted activity. Because of this, it is argued that consumers' ethical perceptions are protected by SEP, and it is possible that they will participate freely, share information, and value co-creation. Ramaswamy, V. and Ozcan, (2016) found that research on the social media environment has confirmed that value co-creation can be fostered by online social. Thus, the hypothesis proposed is:

H6: There is a positive relationship between consumer's ethical perception of SEPs and social value co-creation

In the previous studies, willingness to pay is the result of effective brand management since it reflects the ability to set higher prices for all types of brands than competitors (DeChernatony, L., Segal-Horn, 2003b). The study conducted by (Kroege & Weber, 2014) argued that for social value co-creation in society there needs to be an emphasis on social goals that are in line with the expectations of current society. This includes the willingness for the conformity of the premium price paid. Thus, the hypothesis proposed is:

H7: There is a positive relationship between social value co-creation and willingness to pay premium price.

Based on the literature review, the model can be presented as in Figure 1. The role model of economic and social value co-creation on the relationship between sharing economy platform participation and customer ethical perception with willingness to pay premium. An increase in the sharing economy platform participation and customer ethical perception will trigger an increase in intentions and social value co-creation which ultimately encourages willingness to pay premium price.

Figure 1: The Role Model of Intention and Social value co-creation on Willingness to Pay Premium Based on Customer Participation and Consumer Ethical Perception of SEPs

RESEARCH METHOD

Sample and procedure

The population in this study were consumers of the sharing economy platform services in Central Java, Indonesia. The data were obtained by distributing questionnaires to 450 respondents. The survey was carried out by distributing questionnaires directly to users of the sharing economy platform services both offline and online. After 1 month of the data collection process, only 419 had returned, or around 93.11%. After the received questionnaires being reviewed, 402 questionnaires (89%) could be used for data analysis. The selected respondents consisted of 65.9% female and 34.1% male aged between 16 years to ≥ 45 years. Most of them were consumers or customers of the sharing economy platforms. Most of their education level (66.1%) was high school, 5% diploma, 17.4% undergraduate, and 11.5% postgraduate.

Instrument

Five variables were used to explain the model offered namely customers participation of the sharing economy platform, consumer ethical perception of the sharing economy platform, value co-creation intention, social value co-creation, and willingness to pay premium price. Customer participation in sharing economy platform is customer involvement with the intensity of individual participation which can be interpreted as customer involvement in service production, or provision, or even distribution of information (Auh, S., Bell, S.J., McLeod, C.S., Shih, 2007; Chan, K.W., Yim, C.K., Lam, 2010). Value co-creation intention is value co-creation in services as value co-creation platform, occurs on direct interactions between customers and service providers (Grönroos, 2012). Consumers ethical perception of sharing economy platform relates to the implementation of a marketing code of ethics that can be used as references in marketing activities (Ferrell, O. C., Ferrell, L., & Sawayda, 2015; Gaski, 1999; Schauster, E., & Neill, 2017). Social value co-creation (SVC) is an integration of the interests of various entities including profit and non-profit organizations in society (Ratten, 2020). Social value creation provides a way to focus on how social goals can be adopted in business activities (Di Domenico et al., 2010), thereby providing a link between traditional

commercial entrepreneurial activities and a more socially oriented view to generate profits. The measurement of each instrument uses an interval scale of 1 to 10, a score of 1 indicates strongly disagree with a statement submitted and a score of 10 indicates strongly agree. This scale would also produce a measurement that allows the calculation of mean, standard deviation, statistical parameter test, correlations, etc. as expected by the SEM AMOS program (Ferdinand, 2014).

Analysis Technique

The empirical research model was examined using the structural equation model (SEM). Through this model, the multidimensionality of theoretical constructs (construct validity) was examined using the Confirmatory Factor Analysis Model. In addition, SEM was also used as a comprehensive test tool for the full structural model. Data analysis followed the process suggested by (Joseph F. Hair, William C. Black, Barry J. Babin, 2010), that is, making a path diagram model of the causality relationship between constructs and their indicators, examining the unidimensionality of each construct using confirmatory factor analysis, estimating the full structural model equation for indicators that have passed the confirmatory test, and discussing convergence and discriminant validity before moving to substantive analysis. SEM analysis is performed using Amos software version 23.00.

Table 1: Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results for the Measurement Model

	λ	p-value
Willingness to Pay Premium Price (WPP)		
Paying more expensive for products or services from the SEP which is commonly used	0.698	0.000
Paying extra fees for the product delivery fee set by SEP	0.695	0.000
Paying more expensive for products or services from the SEP which is commonly used	0.716	0.000
Paid presentation for transactions using SEP	0.713	0.000
Value Co-creation Intentions (VCI)		
Providing experiences and suggestions to friends through the SEP used	0.708	0.000
Desiring advice from friends before buying something from SEP	0.700	0.000
Purchasing products/services recommended by friends through SEP	0.714	0.000
Considering friends' buying experience via SEP before buying	0.701	0.000
Customer Participation (CP)		
Providing online SEP information used to other members	0.716	0.000
Posting messages and providing online feedback on the SEP used	0.727	0.000
Actively participating online in SEP activities that commonly used	0.703	0.000
Spending a lot of time to participate online in SEP activities	0.715	0.000
Participating in a commonly used SEP will be good	0.714	0.000
Participating in the SEP that I usually use will be of benefit to me	0.735	0.000
Consumers Ethical Perception of Sharing Economy (CEP)		
Without consent, the SEP will not use personal information	0.708	0.000
The SEP used guarantees consumer personal information	0.713	0.000
The SEP used will not apply special technology	0.734	0.000
The electronic payment system from the SEP used is safe and verified	0.704	0.000
The SEP used to guide consumers to payment steps	0.742	0.000
Consumers receive products /service items according to online messages	0.695	0.000
Social Value Co-creation (SVC)		
SEP used has a good value for the price it sets	0.722	0.000
There are good deals in the commonly used SEPs	0.733	0.000
The SEP used is an economic alternative for service provision	0.702	0.000
The commonly used SEP sets an affordable price	0.724	0.000

$\chi^2 = 272,412$; DF = 245, probability = 0.110, GFI = 0.945, AGFI = 0.932, TLI = 0.991, CFI = 0.992, RMSEA = 0.017, CMIM/DF = 1.112.

FINDINGS

This study reports the results of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) for the complete sample. The observations are conducted on 24 indicators (4 WPP indicators, 4 VCI indicators, 6 CP indicators, 6 CEP indicators, and 4 SVC indicators) to obtain 24 relevant loading factor values (λ_1 - λ_{24}). Unidimensional assessment is conducted by examining general least square standardized estimates of factor loading, which exceeds 0.6 (Hair et al., 2010). In accordance with the existing provisions in AMOS, the loading factors for all observed latent variables have good validity as having values above 0.6 as in table 1.

Construction reliability indicates internal consistency so that the indicators consistently represent the same latent constructs (Hair et al., 2010). Construct reliability (CR) that exceeds 0.7, variance extracted (VE) that exceeds 0.5, and discriminant validity (DV) that exceeds 0.7 are the standards for measuring the internal consistency of the indicators used. Table 2 shows CR value that is greater than 0.7, VE that exceeds 0.5, and the square of AVE that exceeds the correlation value between variables. This indicates that each instrument has good validity in explaining the research variables used.

The testing result of the full structural equation model indicates good Goodness-of-Fit index since it produces criteria as recommended by SEM. The value of X^2 is 272,412 with p-value = 0.110, GFI index of 0.945, AGFI of 0.932, TLI of 0.991, CFI of 0.992 which equals or exceeds 0.90, and other criteria such as RMSEA of 0.017 which is less than 0.08 and CMIM / DF = 1.112 which is less than 2, according to the criteria recommended in SEM. Thus, the recommended model is fit or having the feasibility to examine the relationship between variables.

Table 2: Construct Reliabilities, Correlations, and AVE

N = 402	1	2	3	4	5
1. CP	0.865				
2. VCI	0.123	0.800			
3. CEP	0.051	0.088	0.863		
4. SVC	0.111	0.130	0.118	0.812	
5. WPP	0.020	0.146	0.062	0.149	0.800
Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	0.768	0.667	0.742	0.691	0.664

Factor reliabilities are on the diagonal (italic bold).

Table 3 and Figure 2 show the results of the direct effect of the significant positive effect between **VCI on WPP** (Std β = 0.198, c.r = 3.429, p-value < 0.01), **CP on VCI** (Std β = 0.233, c.r = 3.548, p-value < 0.01), **CP on CEP** (Std β = 0.157, c.r = 2.842, p-value < 0.01), **CEP on VCI** (Std β = 0.175, c.r = 2.564, p-value < 0.01), **CP on SVC** (Std β = 0.194, c.r = 3.149, p < 0.01); **CEP on SVC** (Std β = 0.162, c.r = 2.530, p-value < 0.01), and **SVC on WPP** (Std β = 0.299, c.r = 3.765, p-value < 0.01). Based on the analysis above, it indicates that H1, H2, H3, H4, H6, and H7 are accepted.

Table 3. The Parameter Estimation of the Direct Effect between Model Variables

Hypothesis	Regression	Estimation Value	S.E.	C.R.	Note
H1	VCI → WPP	0.198	0.058	3.429***	Accepted
H2	CP → VCI	0.233	0.066	3.548***	Accepted
H3	CP → CEP	0.157	0.055	2.842***	Accepted
H4	CEP → VCI	0.175	0.068	2.564***	Accepted
H5	CP → SVC	0.194	0.062	3.149***	Accepted
H6	CEP → SVC	0.162	0.064	2.530***	Accepted
H7	SVC → WPP	0.229	0.061	3.765***	Accepted
Note : ***p <0.01					

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between CP, VCI, CEP, and SVC with WPP, as well as the mediating roles of VCI and SVC in the relationship between CP and WPP. This study has proven how important the roles of VCI and SVC in the sharing economy platform (SEP) for consumers pay more for service products made by companies. Based on the hypothesis testing results, H1 is accepted since there is a significant relationship between VCI and WPP. This proves the important role of value co-creation intention, which is customer intention to engage in social behaviour for co-creation in determining premium prices so that consumers are willing to pay. H2 is accepted since there is a positive correlation between CP and VCI that is customer participation has a positive relationship with value co-creation intentions. H3 is accepted since there is a positive relationship between CP and CEP that is customer participation has a positive correlation to consumer ethical perceptions. H4 is accepted since there is a positive relationship between CEP and VCI that is consumer ethical perceptions have a positive correlation with value co-creation intention. H5 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between CP and SVC that is customer participation has a positive effect on social value co-creation in the sharing economy platform. H6 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between CEP and SVC that is consumer ethical perceptions have a positive effect on social value co-creation. H7 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between SVC and WPP that is social value co-creation has a strong effect on the willingness of consumers to pay premium prices on the sharing economy platform.

The significant relationship between CP, CEP, and VCI indicates that VCI plays a mediating role in the relationship between CP, CEP, and WPP. However, several independent variables such as CP, CEP, VCI, and SVC have positive and significant direct relationships with WPP. VCI and SVC have strategic roles in delivering the roles of CP and CEP to increase WPP. The total impact of direct and indirect relationships will be greater than the direct impact. The mediation of VCI and SVC will strengthen the regression relationship between CP and CEP to improve WPP (Rucker, D. D., Preacher, K. J., Tormala, Z. L., & Petty, 2011). Thus, VCI and SVC are significant mediators in the relationship between CP and CEP to WPP.

In the previous study by Nadeem et al., (2020), it is stated that the testing result of the sharing economy platform (SEP) model indicates that social support affects ethical perceptions, which

in turn will affect the value co-creation intention along with satisfaction. If the consumers are satisfied with the SEP, value co-creation may occur. Ethical perceptions also affect trust and commitment, it can be confirmed yet the effect of co-creation intentions. As well, it is found that online social support can lead to satisfaction (Hajli, 2014; Obst, P., Stafurik, 2010), commitment, and trust (Hajli, 2014). This is in line with the current study that the consequences of consumer satisfaction caused by social support will affect purchases in the form of willingness to pay premium prices.

A study in another model testing by Nadeem et al., (2019) found that increased participation in SEP has a positive effect on the increase in ethical perceptions. This is consistent with the existing understanding that consumers enthusiastically adopt SEP services and products (Zervas, G., Proserpio, D., Byers, 2017). Thus, this is in line with the research result which states that customer participation has a positive relationship with consumer ethical perception of sharing economy platform. The study also finds that consumer ethical perceptions in SEP have a significant effect on value co-creation intention in line with the study conducted by (Nadeem et al., 2019).

The direct relationship between consumer participation and value co-creation intention also shows similar results with Hajli, N., Shanmugam, M., Papagiannidis, S., Zahay, D., & Richard & O, (2017) who argued that consumer participation in SEP is an important element of value co-creation. This finding is also in line with the research conducted by (Chae, H., & Ko, 2016; Kamboj, S., & Sarmah, 2018b) where it is stated that consumer participation refers to efforts to achieve value co-creation on the sharing economy platform. Besides that, the research findings are in line with the research conducted by (Schau, H. J., Muñiz, A. M., Jr., & Arnould, 2009) which revealed that consumer participation in online platforms can result in value co-creation (Martinez-Cañas, R., Ruiz-Palomino, P., Linuesa-Langreo, J. & Blázquez-Resino, 2016) while (Kamboj, S., & Sarmah, 2018a) found that consumer participation results in brand co-creation.

From the empirical study, the SEP model is a new reference that provides solutions to the controversy over the relationship between CP, VCI, CEP, and SVC on WPP. The results confirm the roles of internal factors such as CP and CEP in strengthening SVC and VCI. As a SVC internal driver, (1) the existence of CP is needed when the companies require consumer participation in creating new ways in market mechanisms, (2) the existence of CEP is needed when consumer ethical perceptions to support the companies in implementing a market-oriented culture by adopting a code of ethics in its operations, (3) the existence of VCI is needed when the companies continuously apply value co-creation in services as platforms, value co-creation occurs in the direct interactions between customers and service providers.

This study contributes to the efforts to advance the existing research on ethics in the context of sharing economy, that is, marketing ethics literature. Besides, it also to advance the literature on consumer participation in value co-creation (Martinez-Cañas, R., Ruiz-Palomino, P., Linuesa-Langreo, J. & Blázquez-Resino, 2016) and value creation on SEP (Camilleri, J., & Neuhofer, 2017; (Zinko et al., 2017) Zhang, T. C., Jahromi, M. F., & Kizildag, 2018). As well, this study significantly contributes to the literature on marketing ethics and sharing economy

and the direction of the study serves as a basic platform for the study of ethics, participation, and value co-creation in SEP. Therefore, the study provides a significant contribution to the literature on sharing economy. The consequences of this contribution will answer or resolve some of the limitations that have been formulated in the previous studies, especially to know the willingness of consumers to pay premium prices on products with ethical perceptions and consumer participation.

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the findings on participation in SEP are due to consumers' active online participation. The CP, CEP, VCI, and SVC variables have direct and significant relationships with WPP. The findings expand on existing research that is proving the relationship between consumer participation and consumer ethical perceptions, value co-creation intention, and social value creation along with the willingness of consumers to pay premium prices in the sharing economy platform.

Limitations and future research directions

The previous studies have put value co-creation intention as the dependent variable (Nadeem et al., 2019) and consumer ethical perception as the mediating variable between social support and value co-creation (Nadeem et al., 2020). Specifically, this study places value co-creation intention and social value co-creation as mediation in the relationship between customer participation and willingness to pay premium price. In this research, besides contribution, there are limitations to the SEP model, especially in the variables or constructs used. There are several variables such as social commerce information, social support which includes emotional and informational support, and relationship quality to brand co-creation (Tajvidi et al., 2018) which need attention, but an in-depth study has not been conducted as an antecedent variable of willingness to pay premium price. In further research, various antecedents and the consequences of value co-creation concept need to be examined to enrich the literature on sharing economy platforms, especially on marketing ethics and consumer participation in value co-creation.

REFERENCES

- ❖ Agag, G. (2019). E-commerce ethics and its impact on buyer repurchase intentions and loyalty: An empirical study of small and medium Egyptian businesses. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 154(2), 389–410.
- ❖ Algesheimer, R., Dholakia, U. M., & Herrmann, A. (2005). The social influence of brand community: Evidence from European car clubs. *Journal of Marketing*, 69(3), 19–34.
- ❖ Auh, S., Bell, S.J., McLeod, C.S., Shih, E. (2007). Co-production and customer loyalty in financial services. *J. Retail*, 83(3), 359–370.
- ❖ Belk, R. (2014). You are what you can access: sharing and collaborative consumption online. *J. Bus. Res.*, 67(8), 1595–1600.
- ❖ Bendapudi, N., & Leone, R. P. (2003). Psychological implications of customer participation in co-production. *Journal of Marketing*, 67(1), 14–28.
- ❖ Botsman, R., Rogers, R. (2011). *What's Mine is Yours: How Collaborative Consumption Is Changing the Way We Live*. 5 Collins,.
- ❖ Breidert, C., Hahsler, M. and Reutterer, T. (2006). A review of methods for measuring willingness-to-pay”.

- Innovative Marketing, 2(4), 8–32.
- ❖ Bucher, E., Fieseler, C., Lutz, C. (2016). What's mine is yours (for a nominal fee) – Exploring the spectrum of utilitarian to altruistic motives for internet-mediated sharing. *Comput. Hum. Behav.*, 62 (Septem), 316–326.
 - ❖ Camilleri, J., & Neuhofer, B. (2017). Value co-creation and co-destruction in the Airbnb sharing economy. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(9), 2322–2340.
 - ❖ Chae, H., & Ko, E. (2016). Customer social participation in the social networking services and its impact upon the customer equity of global fashion brands. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(9), 3804–3812.
 - ❖ Chan, K.W., Yim, C.K., Lam, S. . (2010). Is customer participation in value creation a double-edged sword? Evidence from professional financial services across cultures. *Journal Marketing*, 74(3), 48–64.
 - ❖ Cova, B., Dalli, D. (2009). Working consumers: the next step in marketing theory? *Marketing Theory*, 9(3), 315–339.
 - ❖ Davcik, N. & Sharma, P. (2015). Impact of product differentiation, marketing Investments and brand equity on pricing strategies: a brand level investigation. *European Journal of Marketing*, 49(5-6), 760–781.
 - ❖ De Pelsmacker, P., Driesen, L., Rayp, G. (2005). Do consumers care about ethics? Willingness to pay for fair-trade coffee. *J. Consum. Aff.*, 39(2), 363–385.
 - ❖ DeChernatony, L., Segal-Horn, S. (2003b). The criteria for successful services brands. *Eur.J.Mark.*, 37(7/8), 1095–1118.
 - ❖ Di Domenico, M. L., Haugh, H., & Tracey, P. (2010). Social bricolage: Theorizing social value creation in social enterprises. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 34(4), 681–703. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2010.00370.x>
 - ❖ Dillahun, T.R., Malone, A. . (2015). The promise of the sharing economy among disadvantaged communities. *The Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, April 18–23.
 - ❖ Eckhardt, G., Bardhi, F. (2015). The Sharing Economy Isn't about Sharing at All [Homepage of Harvard Business Review] [Online]. Available. <https://Hbr.Org/2015/01/the-Sharing-Economy-Isnt-about-Sharing-at-All> [2017, 3/22].
 - ❖ Eckhardt, G.M., Bardhi, F. (2016). The relationship between access practices and economic systems. *J. Assoc. Consum. Res.*, 1(2), 210–225.
 - ❖ Ferdinand, A. (2014). *Management Research Method: a research guidance for writing thesis and dissertation in management science* (5th ed.). Undip Press - Badan Penerbitan Undip.
 - ❖ Ferrell, O. C., Ferrell, L., & Sawayda, J. (2015). A review of ethical decision-making models in marketing ((Ed.), In). *Handbook on ethics & marketing*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
 - ❖ Firat, A. F., & Venkatesh, A., & Firat, A. F., & Venkatesh, A. (1993). Postmodernity: The age of marketing. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 10(3), 227–249.
 - ❖ Fleischman Foreit, K.G. and Foreit, J. R. (2004). *Willingness to Pay Surveys for Setting Prices for Reproductive Health Products and Services*, Population Council, Washington, DC.
 - ❖ Gaski, J. F. (1999). Does marketing ethics really have anything to say? A critical Inventory of the literature. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 18(3), 315–334.
 - ❖ Grönroos, C. (2012). Conceptualising value co-creation: a journey to the 1970 and back to the future *Journal. Marketing Management*, 28(13-14), 1520–1534.
 - ❖ Hajli, N., Shanmugam, M., Papagiannidis, S., Zahay, D., & Richard, M., & O. (2017). Branding co-creation

- with members of online brand communities. *Journal of Business Research*, 70(1), 136–144.
- ❖ Hajli, M. N. (2014). The role of social support on relationship quality and social commerce. *Technol. Forecast. Social Change*, 87, 17–27.
 - ❖ Homburg, C., Koschate, N., Hoyer, W. . (2005). Do satisfied customers really pay more? A study of the relationship between customer satisfaction and willingness to pay. *Journal Marketing*, 69(2), 84–96.
 - ❖ Huang, R., Kim, H., & Kim, J. (2013). Social capital in QQ China: Impacts on virtual engagement of information seeking, interaction sharing, knowledge creating, and purchasing intention. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 29(3-4), 292–316.
 - ❖ Ind, N., Iglesias, O., & Schultz, M. (2013). Building brands together: Emergence and outcomes of co-creation. *California Management Review*, 55(3), 5–26.
 - ❖ Joseph F. Hair, William C. Black, Barry J. Babin, R. E. A. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (7th ed.). Prentice Hall.
 - ❖ Kamboj, S., & Rahman, Z. (2017). Measuring customer social participation in online travel communities: Scale development and validation. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 8(3), 432–464.
 - ❖ Kamboj, S., & Sarmah, B. (2018a). Construction and validation of the customer social participation in brand communities scale. *Internet Research*, 28(1), 46–73.
 - ❖ Kamboj, S., & Sarmah, B. (2018b). Construction and validation of the customer social participation in brand communities scale. *Internet Research*, 28(1), 46–73.
 - ❖ Kroeger, A., & Weber, C. (2014). Developing a conceptual framework for comparing social value creation. *Academy of Management Review*, 39(4), 513–540. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2012.0344>
 - ❖ Kumar, V., Lahiri, A., Dogan, O. . (2018). A strategic framework for a profitable business model in the sharing economy. *Ind. Mark. Manag.*, 69, 147–160.
 - ❖ Li, G., Li, G., Kambele, Z. (2012). Luxury fashion brand consumers in China: perceived value, fashion lifestyle, and willingness to pay. *Journal Business Research*, 65(10), 1516–1522.
 - ❖ Li, Y., Ding, R., Cui, L., Lei, Z., Mou, J. (2019). The impact of sharing economy practices on sustainability performance in the Chinese construction industry. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, 150. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104409>
 - ❖ Marn, M. V., Roegner, E. V., & Zawada, C. C. (2004). *The Price Advantage* (Vol. 286). John Wiley & Sons.
 - ❖ Marn, M.V., Roegner, E.V. and Zawada, C. . (2003). Pricing new product. *McKinsey Quarterly*, 3(3), 21–30.
 - ❖ Martinez-Cañas, R., Ruiz-Palomino, P., Linuesa-Langreo, J., & Blázquez-Resino, J. J. (2016). Consumer participation in cocreation: An enlightening model of causes and effects based on ethical values and transcendent motives. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 793.
 - ❖ Merlo, O., Eisingerich, A.B., Auh, S. (2014). Why customer participation matters. *MIT Sloan Manage.Rev.*, 55(2), 81–88.
 - ❖ Merz, M.A., Zarantonello, L., Grappi, S. (2018). How valuable are your customers in the brand value co-creation process? The development of a Customer Co-Creation Value (CCCV) scale. *J. Bus.*, 82, 79–89.
 - ❖ Mittendorf, C. (2016). What trust means in the sharing economy: A provider perspective on Airbnb.com. In *Proceedings of the 22nd Americas Conference on Information Systems*.
 - ❖ Miyazaki, A. D., & Fernandez, A. (2001). Consumer perceptions of privacy and security risks for online shopping. *The Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 35(1), 27–44.
 - ❖ Möhlmann, M. (2015). Collaborative consumption: determinants of satisfaction and the likelihood of using a

- sharing economy option again. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 14(3), 193–207.
- ❖ Nadeem, W., Juntunen, M., Hajli, N., & Tajvidi, M. (2019). The Role of Ethical Perceptions in Consumers' Participation and Value Co-creation on Sharing Economy Platforms. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 0123456789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04314-5>
 - ❖ Nadeem, W., Juntunen, M., Shirazi, F., & Hajli, N. (2020). Consumers' value co-creation in sharing economy: The role of social support, consumers' ethical perceptions and relationship quality. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 151(October 2019), 119786. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119786>
 - ❖ Nambisan, S., & Nambisan, P. (2008). How to profit from a better' virtual customer environment'. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 49(3), 53.
 - ❖ Obst, P., Stafurik, J. (2010). Online we are all able bodied: online psychological sense of community and social support found through membership of disability-specific websites promotes well-being for people living with a physical disability. *J. Community Appl. Soc. Psychol.*, 20(6), 525–531.
 - ❖ O'Hern, M. S., & Rindfleisch, A. (2010). Customer co-creation. *Review of Marketing Research*. Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 84–106.
 - ❖ Pai, P. Y., & Tsai, H. T. (2011). How virtual community participation influences consumer loyalty intentions in online shopping contexts: An investigation of mediating factors. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 30(5), 603–615.
 - ❖ Palmatier, R.W., Scheer, L.K., Steenkamp, J.-B. . (2007). Customer loyalty to whom? Managing the benefits and risks of sales person-owned loyalty. *Journal Marketing Research*, 44(2), 185–199.
 - ❖ Pandey, N. , Mehta, N. , Roy, S. B. (2016). Semiconductor pricing strategy in USB market: a market leader's dilemma. *Business Perspect. Res*, 5(1), 1–10.
 - ❖ Park, K. C. (2018). Understanding ethical consumers: willingness-to-pay by moral cause. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 35(2), 157–168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-02-2017-2103>
 - ❖ Perren, R., & Kozinets, R. V. (2018). Lateral exchange markets: How social platforms operate in a networked economy. *Journal of Marketing*, 82(1), 20–36.
 - ❖ Ramaswamy, V., Ozcan, K. (2016). Brand value co-creation in a digitalized world: an integrative framework and research implications. *International Journal Research Marketing*, 33(1), 93–106.
 - ❖ Rao, A.R. , Bergen, M. . (1992). Price premium variations as a consequence of buyers' lack of information. *J. Consum. Res.*, 19(3), 412–423.
 - ❖ Ratten, V. (2020). Coronavirus (covid-19) and social value co-creation. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-06-2020-0237>
 - ❖ Román, S., & Cuestas, P. J. (2008). The perceptions of consumers regarding online retailers' ethics and their relationship with consumers' general internet expertise and word of mouth: A preliminary analysis. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 83(4), 641–656.
 - ❖ Rucker, D. D., Preacher, K. J., Tormala, Z. L., & Petty, R. E. (2011). Mediation Analysis in Social Psychology: Current Practices and New Recommendations. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 5(6), 359–371.
 - ❖ Sánchez, J., Callarisa, L., Rodríguez, R.M., Moliner, M. . (2006). Perceived value of the purchase of a tourism product. *Tour. Manag*, 27(3), 394–409.
 - ❖ Schau, H. J., Muñiz, A. M., Jr., & Arnould, E. J. (2009). How brand community practices create value. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(5), 30–51.
 - ❖ Schauster, E., & Neill, M. (2017). Have the ethics changed? An examination of ethics in advertising and public

- relations agencies. *Journal of Media Ethics*, 32(1), 45–60.
- ❖ Schor, J.B., Fitzmaurice, C., Carfagna, L.B., Attwood-Charles, W., Poteat, E. . (2016). Paradoxes of openness and distinction in the sharing economy. *Poetics* 54, 66–81.
 - ❖ Shao, J., & Ünal, E. (2019). What do consumers value more in green purchasing? Assessing the sustainability practices from demand side of business. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 209, 1473–1483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.11.022>
 - ❖ Sundararajan, A. (2016). *The Sharing Economy: the End of Employment and the Rise of Crowd-based Capitalism*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA. sustainability performance in the Chinese construction industry. Sundararajan, A., 150. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104409>.
 - ❖ Sutherland, W., & Jarrahi, M. H. (2018). The sharing economy and digital platforms: review and research agenda. *International Journal of Information Management*, 43, 328–341.
 - ❖ Sweeney, J.C., Soutar, G. . (2001). Consumer Perceived Value: The Development of a Multiple Item Scale. *Journal Retailing*, 77(2), 203–220.
 - ❖ Tajvidi, M., Richard, M. O., Wang, Y. C., & Hajli, N. (2018). Brand co-creation through social commerce information sharing: The role of social media. *Journal of Business Research*, January. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.06.008>
 - ❖ Talwar, R., & Ali, S. W. (2016). Ethical issues in insurance marketing in India: The policy holders' view. *SIBM Pune Research Journal*, XI(June), 1–12.
 - ❖ Vargo, S. L., & Lusch, R. F. (2016). Institutions and axioms: An extension and update of service-dominant logic. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 44(5), 5–23.
 - ❖ Vargo, S.L., Lusch, R. F. (2004). Service-dominant logic: continuing the evolution. *Journal Marketing*, 68(1), 1–17.
 - ❖ Veloutsou, C., & Moutinho, L. (2009). Brand relationships through brand reputation and brand tribalism. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(3), 314–322.
 - ❖ Wang, Y., po lo, H., Chi, R., & Yang, Y. (2004). An integrated framework for customer value and customer-relationship-management performance: A customer-based perspective from China. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 14(2), 169–182. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520410528590>
 - ❖ We-Economy. (2015). *Your Business in the We-Economy*. <https://Www.Smartcitiesdive.Com/Ex/Sustainablecitiescollective/We-Economy-Value-Creation-Age-Networks/1087581>.
 - ❖ Zach, W. Y. L., Chan, T. K. H., Balaji, M. S., & Chong, A. Y.-L. (2018). Why people participate in the sharing economy: An empirical investigation of Uber. *Internet Research*, 28(3), 829–850.
 - ❖ Zervas, G., Proserpio, D., Byers, J. . (2017). The rise of the sharing economy: estimating the impact of Airbnb on the hotel industry. *Journal Marketing Research*, 54(5), 687–705.
 - ❖ Zhang, T. C., Jahromi, M. F., & Kizildag, M. (2018). Value co-creation in a sharing economy: The end of price wars. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 71, 51–58.
 - ❖ Zinko, R., Furner, Z. Z., Hunt, J., & Dalton, A. (2017). Establishing a Reputation. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 54(2), 87–96. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joec.12056>
 - ❖ Zwass, V. (2010). Co-creation: toward a taxonomy and an integrated research perspective. *Int. J. Electron. Commer*, 15(1), 11–48.